

D7. 2 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan II

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Abstract	Deliverable D7.2, the "Updated Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan", builds upon the initial strategy established in D7.1 by providing a refined and more detailed overview of ELOQUENCE's ongoing efforts to engage target audiences, share results, and amplify project impact. This updated version reflects the progress made during the first 18 months of implementation, incorporating revised timelines, tools, and key performance indicators (KPIs), while also highlighting new activities and partner contributions. As a living document, D7.2 ensures continued alignment with the project's evolving objectives and prepares the ground for the final iteration to be delivered in D7.3.		

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4EU	Artificial Intelligence for Europe
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AIJ	Journal of Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation
ALT-EDIC	Alliance for Language Technologies European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan
DOA	Description of action
EU	European Union
EurAI	European Association for Artificial Intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPT	Generative Pre-trained Transformer
GPUs	Graphics Processing Units
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Interactive Playground
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JAIR	Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research
JMLR	Journal of Machine Learning Research
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LLM	Large Language Models
LSPs	Language Service Providers
ML	Machine Learning
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MVP	Minimum Viable Performance
NLP	Natural Language Processing
SEO	Search Engine Optimized

1 Introduction

This document presents the updated Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan for the ELOQUENCE project based on the INOSENS *know-how*, building upon the structure and content established in the initial version from M3 (*Deliverable D7.1*). The updated DEC outlines refinements to communication and outreach strategies, considering project progress, results achieved, and evolving stakeholder needs. Below is a concise overview of the main chapters included in this updated deliverable:

- Chapter 1: **Introduction** – This chapter provides a brief overview, establishing the backdrop for the DEC Plan and its foundational pillars.
- Chapter 2: **Objectives** – In this section, there are lists and updates of the main goals included in the DEC Plan to match where the project is currently at and to strengthen the plan's goals.
- Chapter 3: **Target Audiences** – Within this chapter we identify and pinpoint target groups and stakeholders that we should reach, providing valuable insights into the key individuals and groups crucial for our communication strategy.
- Chapter 4: **ELOQUENCE Integrated Dissemination and Communication Strategies** – This chapter presents the core of the DEC plan as it outlines the diverse outreach approaches, spanning branding and multimedia conceptualization, digital correspondence, involvement in social media, skill enhancement, academic connections, and concluding with tactics for EU-level collaboration and policy impact.
- Chapter 5: **Comms & Dissemination Timeline** – This section outfits an update of the timeline of all communication activities, with the goal of ensuring a timely and effective outreach strategy.
- Chapter 6: **Reporting, Monitoring, Evaluation** – A vital segment highlighting repetitious feedback. This chapter clarifies the structures implemented to evaluate and improve project's dissemination and communication endeavors.
- Chapter 7: **Exploitation Pathway** – This final chapter discusses the avenues and methods to capitalize on the project's results, ensuring the sustainability and impact of ELOQUENCE's contributions well beyond its duration.

The Annexes include:

→ The dissemination and communication reporting template: This is the template that all partners need to update on a monthly basis with information about all the dissemination and communication activities.

With these chapters, the DEC Plan for the ELOQUENCE project offers a comprehensive roadmap, ensuring the project's narratives and outcomes find resonance across a spectrum of audiences and sectors.

2 Objectives

As the ELOQUENCE project reaches its mid-point (M18), the objectives of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan remain closely aligned with the project’s mission to promote trustworthy, multilingual, and human-centric AI technologies. At this stage, our focus has shifted from laying the foundations of the strategy to actively executing and refining activities based on emerging results and stakeholder engagement such as academia, industry leaders, and policy influencers.

Our strategy for internal dissemination within the ELOQUENCE consortium prioritizes consistent communication. To achieve this, we have implemented protocols established in the Grant Agreement, ensuring efficient sharing of information among project partners. This involves adhering to notice periods for upcoming publications and providing opportunities for feedback. Utilizing communication tools such as dedicated project platforms and consortium mailing lists facilitates rapid updates and discussions within our network.

ELOQUENCE's DEC Plan expertly integrates the Communication and Dissemination Plan with the Exploitation Plan, which also incorporates the IPR Management Strategy. This comprehensive blueprint is designed to cater to a diverse audience, establishing clear milestones for each stage. Aligned with the Description of Action (DoA), the fundamental principles of the ELOQUENCE DEC Plan are summarized as follows:

Table 1 DEC Plan - Objectives

#	Objective description
1	Maximize outreach for our Interactive Playground and models by bringing together a large stakeholder group through targeted messaging and customized content.
2	Disseminate scientific knowledge and innovation produced by ELOQUENCE and connect them with various real-world high-risk business cases within the European Language Technology landscape.
3	Share our results and best practices with the European R&D community through various channels, including the AI-on-demand platform, Common European Data Spaces (especially the dedicated Language Data Space), and other relevant digital resource platforms such as Open GPT-X. Our aim is to enhance the European AI, Data and Robotics ecosystem by promoting the sharing of valuable insights and knowledge.
4	Gather insights from target audience segments and prospective users to ensure our technological progress and innovations align with market demands and iterate accordingly to enhance the uptake of innovative language technology solutions by European companies.
5	Pave the way for smooth exploitation of our solutions and other exploitable results to ensure quick pre-commercial-scale deployment of the technology.

3 Target audiences

The target audience for ELOQUENCE has been thoroughly mapped and outlined in Deliverable D7.1. While the consortium recognizes the importance of communicating project activities and outcomes to a wide audience, D7.1 identifies specific groups to target, ensuring the efficiency and impact of the communication and dissemination strategy. For guidance purposes, we are revisiting and outlining the target audience here to provide clear direction and alignment for ongoing and future dissemination activities.

Table 2 Breakdown of Target Stakeholder Groups for the ELOQUENCE Project Classified Based on Their Level of Interest and Impact

Target group	Stakeholder Profiles	Examples	Expected Impact
Researchers and developers in the field of who are interested in advancing the state-of-the art in these areas.	Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning (ML), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) researchers and developers	Academic institutions: Research hubs in NLP, ML, AI. Emerging companies Communities of developers and researchers	Advancements in NLP techniques: Resulting in improved language understanding and translation systems. Increased AI adoption Cross-disciplinary collaborations: Fostering synergies between NLP, ML, and AI researchers
Companies and organizations that develop and use NLP and ML technologies	Companies that are using search engines, virtual assistants, and chatbots.	Smart Home industry producers Virtual agents and assistant providers AI based call centers	Improved user experiences with search engines, virtual assistants, and chatbots. Streamlined customer support processes with AI-based call centers Expansion of multilingual support capabilities.
Language Service Providers (LSPs)	Companies Language Service Providers (LSPs). Users requiring translation or language-related assistance	Translation agencies Companies providing professional translation services Businesses adapting products or services for specific linguistic and cultural markets.	Improved communication and accessibility: Enhanced language services enable businesses and individuals to overcome language barriers, facilitating global interactions and collaborations. Enhanced efficiency and productivity: Access to high-quality language services streamlines workflows and processes, saving time and resources for both LSPs and their clients.
Language educators who are interested in integrating NLP and ML technologies into language learning and teaching.	Educational institutions: Language learning technology developers: Companies and individuals creating tools and platforms	Language schools integrate NLP and ML into courses for improved learning outcomes Professional development programs train educators to implement these technologies in teaching	Enhanced accessibility: Language learning tools using NLP and ML accommodate various learning styles. Innovative teaching methods: NLP and ML integration in language education drives new teaching approaches.

Linguists who are studying language and communication and are interested in the implications of NLP and ML technologies on language and society.

Researchers and scholars specializing in the study of language
Academic institutions

Academic departments within universities conducting research; Teams of researchers investigating the social aspects of language use and communication

Engagement between linguists, technologists, and social scientists fosters interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange; Exploration of NLP and ML technologies contributes to a deeper understanding of language structure, variation, and change, enriching linguistic theory and analysis.

Individuals and communities who may benefit from improved language technologies, such as those with disabilities that affect communication, or those who are not native speakers of a language.

Non-native speakers: Individuals seeking language assistance or translation support to communicate effectively in a language that is not their native tongue.

Organizations advocating for the rights and needs of individuals with disabilities
Online platforms offering language learning resources and tools tailored to the needs of non-native speakers

Enhanced inclusivity through technology development aligned with European values and sustainability, promoting a human-centered approach.

Regulators and policymakers who are interested in developing policies and regulations that govern the use of NLP and ML technologies.

Government agencies, legislators, and policymakers oversee and develop regulations governing the ethical use of NLP and ML technologies.

Lawmakers in national and regional governments who draft and pass legislation addressing the ethical and responsible use of NLP and ML technologies.

Implementation of clear regulations promoting responsible use of NLP and ML
Fostering industry growth while addressing societal concerns.

European Commission, the European Language Technology activities, AI on Demand Platform and EU, Common EU data spaces and related R&I projects

CNECT.G3's Multilingualism Sector
Organizations and research institutions
Platforms and initiatives facilitating access to AI technologies

Academic institutions and research centers collaborating with the European Commission
Emerging companies leveraging AI and language technologies
Collaborative research projects funded by the European Union

Enhanced multilingual communication
Accelerated AI innovation: Access to AI resources through EU platforms

With the progress into implementation of the ELOQUENCE project, target audiences are systematically sorted and ranked so that communication efforts are well-focused and effective. For guidance, we use a **Stakeholder Classification Model** to help us plan better engagement and impact strategies. The assessment process uses the following aspects to measure stakeholders:

- Influence and authority in the areas or policies that affect the company.
- Level of care about the project's intentions, steps taken and what results are promised.
- Trampled roles in the project might be, either by taking part, consulting or by collaborating.
- Ability to affect or respond to findings from projects, mainly linked to deployment, uptake or policy.

This classification system helps us **tailor our communication and engagement approaches** to fit each group's unique role and interests.

4 ELOQUENCE Integrated Dissemination & Communication Strategies

In accordance with the Grant Agreement No. 101135916, as outlined on pages 126 and 128/180, all dissemination and communication activities are categorized into distinct primary clusters. This chapter provides a succinct overview of these groupings.

4.1 Digital Communication and Outreach

4.1.1 Website

The ELOQUENCE website (eloquenceai.eu) continues to serve as the cornerstone of online presence and plays a pivotal role as the presentation of all use cases, project’s progress update, as well as post-project exploitation. Intended to maintain transparency, accessibility and involve partners, the website supports regular exchanges with researchers, industry, government and anyone interested. All sections of the website are arranged to demonstrate the project’s work and activities, offering special pages for news, publications, events, pilots and contributions by experts. The website has been carefully searching engine optimization (SEO) with specific keywords placed throughout the pages, helping people find it in web search engine results.

Ranking **5,429** site visitors so far with **34,594** event counts, this platform offers essential information about the ELOQUENCE concept and methodology, technical approaches, pilots and news and event information. United States accounted for the highest number of active users, followed by United Kingdom, India, Italy and Netherlands.

Figure 1 ELOQUENCE Website’s Active User Overview by Country

The structure of the website was further updated compared to the last reporting period (D7.1) organized into multiple pages to ensure user-friendly navigation and seamless user experience. The ELOQUENCE website is organized into the following pages:

1. **Home page:** The "Home" page of the ELOQUENCE website serves as the first point of contact for visitors, offering a concise but informative introduction to the project's goals, approach, and vision for the future of multilingual AI agent technologies. It outlines how ELOQUENCE aims to address the limitations of current large language models by developing multilingual, trustworthy, and context-aware AI agents that support inclusive communication, reduce bias, and ensure transparency in high-stakes applications across Europe. The page highlights the six core building blocks that define the project's objectives, emphasizing the integration of innovative solutions, stakeholder collaboration, and legal alignment. A dynamic slider showcases the project’s partners, providing links to their dedicated pages, which gives users easy access to further details about the institutions involved.

Figure 2 Brief overview of the ELOQUENCE home page

2. **About page:** The focus is on the key characteristics of the ELOQUENCE project divided into three sections:

- **Who we are page:** This page introduces the ELOQUENCE consortium to visitors. It provides a brief overview of the consortium and its origins, which are directly linked to their respective institution pages within the ELOQUENCE website.
- **Community of Experts:** This page presents each expert of the Community which will in later project phases provide assessment of emerging technologies and ensure respect for European values (i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety). Experts are divided into full members, consortium members and alternative members.
- **Synergies:** Since ELOQUENCE recognizes opportunities for collaboration and potential for synergies, not only within projects funded under the same topic but also between those funded under different topics, clusters, or pillars of Horizon Europe and beyond, we have created a subpage to showcase our current connections. This page highlights our collaborations with three other EU-funded projects and one EU based startup.

Figure 3 Brief overview of the About page sections

- Pilots:** This page provides information about all the piloting partners. Their work, methodology, challenges and milestones. In further stages of the project, this page will have its own subpage for each pilot.

Figure 4 Sections where ELOQUENCE pilots will be placed

- Events:** The "Events" section, with currently **30 events**, represents a dynamic calendar containing information about date, time, location, and links for registrations, allowing stakeholders to integrate events into their schedules. This calendar interface provides a comprehensive view of both past and upcoming events, facilitating easy access to accompanying materials such as PDFs, links, and multimedia resources.

Figure 5 Appearance of the Events page

5. **Newsroom/Insight Hub:** This section compiles blog posts that, while not scientific papers like those found on the “*Publication*” page, remain pertinent to the ELOQUENCE project and its activities, developments and news from the European Union related topics. Currently this page contains **60 blog posts**.

Figure 6 Insight Hub gathers partners activity and relevant subjects

6. **Resources:** The Resources section is designed to serve as a central repository for all publicly available outputs, materials, and documentation produced throughout the project. This section aims to support knowledge sharing, transparency, and community engagement by offering easy access to valuable project-related content. Also, it contains libraries for media coverage, collaboration and alliances related to ELOQUENCE and newsletter subscription option. Designed to give stakeholders and visitors direct access to our milestones, deliverables, policy briefs, publications, presentations, keynotes, and the latest technical releases. It contains five blocks divided into the following:

- **AI Dictionary:** It provides a brief overview of the most common terms in AI for those new to the subject or needing clarification on commonly used jargon. It features clear and concise explanations of terminology like artificial intelligence, neural networks, deep learning, machine learning, algorithm, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning or natural language processing, among others. This dictionary could be used as a reference guide to demystify complex AI concepts, facilitate communication among professionals, and aid students and enthusiasts in their learning journey within the discipline of AI.
- **Deliverables:** It systematically organizes and categorizes results, providing the foundational groundwork for subsequent deliverables which are public, and enabling their analysis, dissemination, and exploitation.
- **Publications & Presentations:** This page offers visitors access to all publications currently released under the project, including scientific papers and articles. In addition, the page features project newsletters and posters from events where ELOQUENCE has been presented, providing a comprehensive overview of its dissemination efforts and research contributions.

- **Media Center:** It serves as a hub for press and media-related content. This page announces and links news articles, press mentions, and media coverage where the ELOQUENCE project is featured, helping visitors stay informed about the project’s visibility and outreach across external platforms.
 - **Policy Briefs & Standardization:** The page is currently under construction. Once completed, it will feature key standardization documents prepared by our partner PRIVANOVA, as well as guidelines and resources related to standardization processes relevant to the ELOQUENCE project.
7. **Contact:** Offers interested groups direct contact points of ELQUENCE along with social media platforms.
 8. **Imprint:** Page contains a statement of ownership and authorship related to the project.
 9. **Privacy policy:** Contains a statement that describes how a website collects, uses, and manages the personal data of consumers.

4.2 Promotional Material

As addressed in Deliverable 7.1, a comprehensive set of promotional materials was developed in M03, with a strong emphasis on digital-first approaches. This strategy ensures minimal environmental impact, with printed materials produced only when necessary. In such cases, we adopt eco-friendly practices, including the use of recycled paper, environmentally friendly inks, and waste reduction measures. These efforts align with our commitment to reducing our ecological footprint and promoting sustainable practices in all aspects of our communication and dissemination efforts.

Our digital materials continue to include engaging visuals, informative videos, interactive presentations, and intuitive brochures. These resources are designed to effectively convey the project's goals, achievements, and key messages to diverse target audiences. By prioritizing digital formats, we ensure broader reach and facilitate easy sharing and accessibility of information.

Figure 7 Brief overview of the Resource page and its sections

Since the last reporting period, the ELOQUENCE brochure has been updated and is now available in English language, as presented in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

Figure 8 Latest ELOQUENCE brochure

4.3 Social Media Platforms

Following the strategy outlined in Deliverable 7.1, ELOQUENCE has continued to focus on establishing a robust social media presence and fostering two-way communication with target audiences and the wider public. The seven following media channels: LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, BlueSky, YouTube, TikTok and Instagram, were selected based on three key factors:

- **Cost-effectiveness** in promptly sharing project updates with all stakeholder groups.
- **Relevance and influence** of the media channels for disseminating novel practices to a broad range of stakeholders.
- **Popularity and usage** among ELOQUENCE partners for effective communication and interaction with their networks.

Details about the target audience for each social media channel and their specific goals can be found in **Table 3**.

Table 3 Social Media Channels Overview: Target Audiences and Content Strategy for ELOQUENCE

Media	People	Content	Best fit for
	General Public, All Age Groups	Posts, Videos, Events	Broad Outreach, Community Building, Events Sharing
	General Public, All Age Groups	Videos, Tutorials	Demonstrations, Tutorials, Project Videos

	Younger Demographics, Visual Audiences	Images, Stories, Reels	Visual Showcasing, Updates, Engaging with Younger Audience
	General Public, News Followers, Professionals	Tweets, Threads, Videos	News Updates, Quick Announcements, Engaging in Conversations
	Professionals, Researchers	B2B, Articles, Networking Events	Updates, Networking, B2B Engagement, Knowledge Sharing
	Younger Demographics, Visual Audiences	Short video forms	Engaging with Younger Audience, Targeting larger audience with focus on publicity
	Scientific Community, Professionals, Researchers	Post, Images, Articles	Community Building, Updates, Knowledge Sharing

Each social media page has been branded consistently according to our brand book guidelines, ensuring a uniform look and feel across all platforms through covers, media, and other elements.

Since M01, these platforms have been actively updated with fresh and relevant content. The platform’s integrated metrics tools have aided in monitoring post-performance and implementing improvements where necessary. Leveraging the established social media networks of consortium partners has further amplified visibility and impact. In this reporting period, new efforts have been made to enhance content quality and outreach. To drive traffic, increase exposure and engage a broader audience several social media campaigns were developed, and the most notable ones are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Social Media Campaigns: Content Strategy for development of ELOQUENCE

Campaign	Objective
Meet Our Partners	Introducing consortium partners through engaging posts, fostering transparency, trust, and collaboration while showcasing the expertise driving ELOQUENCE’s mission.
International Days	ELOQUENCE leverages key international and UN observance days (e.g., International Day of Multilingualism, Human Rights Day, International Women’s Day) to align its communication efforts with global initiatives, raise awareness of ethical and inclusive language technologies, and highlight the project’s contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
Women in AI Campaign	Showcasing prominent women in the field of artificial intelligence, aligning with ELOQUENCE’s inclusivity goals and promotion of the <i>ELOQUENCE’s Webcafe with Saskia Lensink</i> and podcast episode “ <i>Redefining Human-Computer Interaction: A conversation with Agnese Augello</i> ”

Synergy Campaign	Highlighting collaborations with other projects, mutually sharing project updates, strengthening partnerships and expanding the network of engaged audiences.
ELOQUENCE publications & partners achievement	Sharing partners articles about the project, amplifying reach and affirming the project's relevance in the machine learning and speech recognition domain. Also, we have shared personal partners achievements as a measure of support and motivation.
Newsletter Campaign	Sharing key project updates, insights, and upcoming events via newsletters, driving website traffic and stakeholder engagement.
Event Organization/Participation	Promoted organized and attended events, boosting visibility, event registration and securing mentions in industry-specific publications.
Partners in Action	Showcasing the progress made by consortium partners, such as deploying monitoring tools and data systems, to highlight on-the-ground project developments.
Friday Facts	ELOQUENCE launched the "Friday Facts" campaign across social media platforms to raise awareness and improve public understanding of key concepts in artificial intelligence. Every Friday, we highlight terms from the AI Dictionary available on the ELOQUENCE website, offering concise explanations aimed at making technical language more accessible to a broader audience.

Project partners have consistently provided updates on their activities, which have been shared across ELOQUENCE communication platforms using visually engaging and concise messaging to enhance clarity and impact. In addition, consortium members have promoted the project through their own institutional channels, further amplifying the dissemination of results and expanding the project's overall reach.

4.3.1 LinkedIn

In line with the strategy outlined in Deliverable 7.1, ELOQUENCE continues to strengthen its [LinkedIn](#) presence, posting three times per week updates and offering a platform for individuals to engage with intelligent systems and computational linguistics, including both technical and non-technical aspects. Since its launch, the page has gained **512 followers**, representing a diverse demographic that includes key stakeholders, target groups, and potential collaborators within the water allocation and management value chain.

This growth is largely driven by a series of targeted social media campaigns, detailed in Table 4, which have significantly expanded our reach. Notably, the "ELOQUENCE publications & partners achievement" campaign has successfully informed stakeholders and potential end-users of the project's milestones, while the month-long "Women in AI" campaign has contributed to increased registration and engagement for the associated webinar event and spreading awareness about women in STEM fields. Through these campaigns, we have shared news, updates, and stories from the ELOQUENCE ecosystem on our LinkedIn page and across various LinkedIn groups focused on AI, machine learning, large language models and speech recognitions. Groups such as the "Emotional AI", "Analytics / Data Science / AI Career", "Technology Investor Club: Artificial Intelligence, Data Science, Fintech, IoT, Robotics & Cloud AI", "HORIZON EUROPE " Framework Programme for Research and Innovation", "Agentic AI, Generative AI, Machine Learning, Data Science, Web, Business Analytics, Power BI Copilot", "Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Robotics, DataOps, Gen AI", "Artificial Intelligence Investors Group: Robotics, AI & IoT, Machine Learning, NLP & Computer Vision", "Analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Marketing and Retail", "BIG DATA: Telecom, Intelligence, Analytics, Security, Science, Machine Learning, AI, IoT, Blockchain", "Artificial Intelligence Exchange: AI Conversations and Collaborations" have significantly extended the

reach of our content and facilitated broader discussions on project's related topics. These groups in total have more than **three million members**.

As the project progresses, the list of relevant groups will be periodically updated, opening up new opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange. Join us on LinkedIn to stay updated and participate in the ongoing conversation about climate-smart water allocation and management.

Figure 9 Screenshot of the ELOQUENCE LinkedIn Cover, showcasing brand consistency across digital platforms

4.3.2 Facebook

Since its creation, the ELOQUENCE [Facebook page](#) has been updated three times per week, with **38 followers** engaged in discussions around intelligent systems and computational linguistics. Although Facebook offers broad reach and targeting capabilities, its effectiveness for promoting project results has been limited, as the platform is no longer widely used by our target audiences. By delivering both professional and trustworthy content, ELOQUENCE ensures it communicates in a way that resonates with our target audiences, from industry professionals to local stakeholders. Through a diverse range of content marketing campaigns, including infographics, short videos, and success stories, we continue to share relevant and impactful campaigns.

These campaigns not only drive awareness but also support the development of a strong and collaborative ecosystem for multilinguality and multimodality, Facebook's ability to facilitate long-term content visibility ensures that our messages continue to reach and engage key audiences, helping to advance the project's objectives.

4.3.3 X (Formerly Twitter)

Since its establishment, we have acquired **280 followers** on our [X page](#) - @eloquenceai. We remain committed to establishing thought leadership in the field of artificial intelligence and biases. Our focus continues to be on connecting with industry innovators who contribute to the creation, development, and scalability of ELOQUENCE's pilot solutions. Our X page is updated three times per week with tailored content offering high-quality insights and key trends. Stay informed and engaged by following trending hashtags such as #ELOQUENCEAI, #HorizonEU, #NLP, #ML, #LLM, #SpeechRecognition, #Research and #Collaboration.

Figure 10 Screenshot of the ELOQUENCE X Cover, showcasing brand consistency across digital platforms

4.3.4 BlueSky

BlueSky is the latest established social media for the ELOQUENCE project. Although it is not planned in Grant Agreement, INOSENS, together with consortium partners, decided to open and announce project’s presence at this [platform](#). By tracking the current events, many Twitter users migrated to Bluesky due to dissatisfaction with changes and concerns about the platform's direction. Bluesky, a platform with decentralized architecture and a focus on user-driven content, offered an alternative.

ELOQUENCE’s Bluesky presence is still in its early stages. The account is set up and is publicly accessible and has been updated three times per week, with **226 followers** engaged in discussions around intelligent systems and computational linguistics. Target audiences are primarily early tech adopters, developers, digital rights enthusiasts, and decentralized web advocates. Bluesky profile will be used more for engaging digital ethics conversations—topics aligned with ELOQUENCE’s AI ethics and bias reduction efforts.

4.3.5 Instagram

The ELOQUENCE Instagram [account](#) has served as a visually-driven platform to present the project’s activities, achievements, and human elements in a more informal and accessible way and it **reached 333 followers so far**. With a curated feed focusing on events, partner highlights and campaign visuals, Instagram has been a valuable tool for engaging with audiences who prefer image-based updates over text-heavy formats.

Through regular posts and stories, the account has contributed to shaping the project’s visual identity and reinforcing brand recognition. It has also supported broader dissemination efforts by amplifying blog articles, announcements of webcafés and podcasts, and showcasing the project’s presence at various European events. While not as widely used for formal science communication, Instagram has been instrumental in reaching early-career professionals, students, and stakeholders from creative sectors. It will continue to serve as an important outreach tool, particularly in promoting events, introducing partner teams, and drawing attention to audiovisual content created under various dissemination KPIs.

Figure 11 Screenshot of the ELOQUENCE Instagram Cover, showcasing brand consistency across digital platforms

4.3.6 TikTok

The ELOQUENCE TikTok [account](#) has been established as part of the project’s effort to expand its reach through modern, video-first platforms. While initial activity on TikTok has been limited, the account is strategically positioned to become a key channel for disseminating short, engaging video content developed through several project KPIs, such as explainer videos, webcafés, podcasts, and stakeholder testimonials. Currently, TikTok account has **2 followers and 21 likes**.

TikTok's growing popularity among younger audiences, researchers, and early-career professionals makes it an ideal platform for raising awareness around complex topics like explainable AI, multilingualism, and bias reduction in language models. Its algorithm favors frequent, creative content, offering opportunities for organic reach and audience interaction.

Going forward, ELOQUENCE will increasingly leverage TikTok to share visual narratives tied to key project activities, with a focus on:

- Showcasing highlights from events and conferences
- Sharing concise expert insights from partners
- Repurposing existing video materials (e.g., podcasts, explainer clips)

4.3.7 YouTube

ELOQUENCE’s [Youtube](#) channel was launched in M01 and has gained **37 subscribers**, serving as an effective platform for communicating the project's complex results. Video content is highly engaging and accessible, making it an ideal medium for reaching a diverse range of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, and the general public. So far, the channel has featured **15 videos**:

- First season of podcast series counting six episodes – “ELOQUENCE | Navigating the Intersection of LLMs and Ethical Considerations podcast”
- Two webcafés, one during “Women in AI” campaign in cooperation with sister project TrustLLM – “ELOQUENCE | Webcafe with Saskia Lensink” and one within the project “Trustworthy AI: Why Explainability Matters – Webcafé with Sergio Burdisso”
- Two explainer videos: “ELOQUENCE | Who Are We”, “Ethical AI and Human Rights - Shaping Trustworthy Technologies”
- Four videos of “Virtual Demo Days” session – explaining each of the pilot
- One webinar with webcafe session: “Advancing Multilingual Speech AI Across Europe”

This content has been shared across our social media platforms and website, effectively demonstrating YouTube's benefit of easy shareability and enhancing the project’s visibility across a broader audience. Moving forward, the channel will be regularly updated with additional content, such as recordings from upcoming webinars, events, and pilot activities. All recorded content will be available on the ELOQUENCE YouTube channel, ensuring ongoing access to the project’s findings and activities throughout the project lifecycle, and fostering continued engagement and awareness.

Figure 12 Screenshot of the ELOQUENCE YouTube profile

IMPORTANT NOTE: INO is responsible for the management of **ELOQUENCE social media accounts**. All partners are encouraged to:

- Become a **follower** (like or follow the page/profile)
- **Promote** the accounts within their networks.
- **Recommend profiles** that ELOQUENCE should engage with.
- **Share relevant articles and news** with INO for posting on the project’s social media.
- **Share ELOQUENCE posts and news** on their own organization's social media platforms

4.3.8 Newsletter & Subscriber Engagement

During the first 18 months of the project, 8 newsletters have been distributed. The newsletters showcase the most significant achievements of the project. Subscribers for the ELOQUENCE newsletter can register directly through the project website or via LinkedIn (and other social media accounts), where we actively share newsletters and provide a subscription link to reach a wider audience. This multi-channel approach ensures a user-friendly process and broad dissemination of project updates. To manage and distribute the newsletter, we use the **Brevo platform**, which provides advanced tools for email marketing, communication, and compliance with data protection regulations.

Brevo offers key features that enhance our dissemination efforts, including:

- **Subscriber Management:** Automatic organization of subscriber lists, segmentation for targeted messaging, and GDPR-compliant handling of personal data.
- **Email Design:** Intuitive drag-and-drop editors and customizable templates for visually appealing newsletters.
- **Analytics:** Detailed reports on open rates, click-through rates, and engagement metrics to optimize newsletter performance.
- **Automation:** Scheduled email deliveries and automated follow-ups to ensure timely updates.

Data Security and Compliance

Brevo prioritizes the security and privacy of user data. It employs robust measures such as multi-factor authentication, IP address whitelisting, and encrypted data storage across multiple servers. The platform is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and EU policies, ensuring that all personal data is handled responsibly. Brevo also provides Data Processing Agreements (DPA) to define roles and responsibilities in data handling and offers tools to manage user consent, data portability, and the right to be forgotten.

By leveraging Brevo’s features ELOQUENCE ensures professional, secure, and effective communication with its subscribers, aligning with both project objectives and EU data protection standards.

LinkedIn Newsletter Feature

Although it is not planned in the Grant Agreement, INOSENS is also creating newsletters on this media. LinkedIn’s newsletter feature allows us to create, share, and grow our subscriber base directly on the platform. Key functionalities include:

- **Easy Subscription:** Users can subscribe to the newsletter with a single click, without needing to leave the LinkedIn platform.
- **Automatic Notifications:** Subscribers receive alerts directly in their LinkedIn inbox whenever a new issue is published, ensuring higher visibility and engagement.
- **Built-In Analytics:** LinkedIn provides insights into subscriber demographics, views, and engagement, enabling us to tailor content effectively.

- Professional Network Integration: Leveraging LinkedIn’s professional network allows us to target audiences already interested in our field, enhancing the relevance and reach of the newsletter. By now, our newsletter has garnered **92 engaged subscribers** via Brevo and **222 subscribers** on LinkedIn. The opening rate on Brevo stands at **66.67%**, reflecting strong engagement and interest in our updates. On LinkedIn, the newsletter has achieved **2,144 impressions**, significantly amplifying our reach to a broader professional audience.

This impactful performance demonstrates the success of our multi-channel dissemination strategy, effectively combining Brevo’s advanced email marketing capabilities with LinkedIn’s extensive professional network to maximize visibility and engagement.

INO takes the lead in publishing the newsletter. However, it’s a **collaborative effort**; all partners contribute by supplying content and insights for every issue as directed by the dissemination manager. While the content for each edition is decided collectively by the partners, the general structure, as outlined above, will remain consistent. Upon release, every newsletter is dispatched to all subscribers and a copy can be found at the project’s website.

Figure 13 ELOQUENCE Newsletters available on eloquenceai.eu

4.3.9 Public Relations

4.3.9.1 Media Appearances & Releases

As part of its evolving communication strategy, ELOQUENCE aims to strengthen its visibility and outreach through targeted public relations activities, including media appearances and press releases (KPIs 14, 18, and 29). While large-scale dissemination is anticipated to increase in the upcoming period, particularly following the development and launch of the project’s pilots, initial efforts have already begun. These include the mapping of relevant platforms, news portals, and media channels across Europe, as well as the initiation of tailored communication with key stakeholders. Over the last 18 months, ELOQUENCE has successfully brought attention, **with 13 media articles**

and backlinks published about the project. This, lately increasingly, visibility highlights the growing interest in ELOQUENCE's mission and achievements.

To ensure strategic engagement with a broader audience, INO, in collaboration with project partners, is undertaking the following actions:

- Developing a shared database of relevant media contacts and journalists for future collaboration and story pitching;
- Initiating communication with editors and content managers of identified target platforms to introduce the ELOQUENCE project and its upcoming results;
- Monitoring and recording mentions of the project and its website (eloquenceai.eu) through automated alerts and a dedicated media tracking sheet (see Annex B).

The cultivation of valuable media contacts will be supported by the project's active social media presence and reinforced through direct outreach to journalists, domain experts, and influential stakeholders across relevant sectors. Public relations efforts will be tailored to diverse target audiences, ensuring alignment with the interests and communication preferences of each group. Communication will be disseminated not only through national and international outlets but also via local and regional media to increase grassroots engagement.

The efforts will target pan-European publications and outlets focused on digital innovation, artificial intelligence, language technologies, and responsible tech development. This layered approach will help ELOQUENCE broaden its reach and reinforce its messages across multiple thematic and geographic contexts.

To track media coverage effectively, the consortium has set up Google Alerts for the project and its related keywords. All mentions are systematically documented in the Press Clipping / Media Monitoring Tracker, and noteworthy appearances are featured on the ELOQUENCE website's Media Center.

Partners are encouraged to help analyze media feedback and assist in distributing our press releases.

Press releases for ELOQUENCE are disseminated both on a local level by the local partners, as well as on an international level by the whole consortium. These press releases aim to capture readers from all target groups and are available on the project [website](#).

Figure 14 ELOQUENCE's first two press release

4.4 Capacity Building & Event Management

4.4.1 Media Engagements – Podcasts

ELOQUENCE recognizes the importance of media engagement in effectively disseminating project insights, research outcomes, and sustainable solutions. As part of this strategy, the project has launched a dedicated Podcast Series (KPI 20), offering an engaging and accessible format for presenting expert knowledge, fostering collaboration, and advancing the conversation around conversational AI, machine learning, and natural language processing.

The first season of the “*ELOQUENCE | Navigating the Intersection of LLMs and Ethical Considerations podcast*” has now been successfully completed and is available via the ELOQUENCE YouTube [channel](#). The season features six insightful episodes covering a wide range of themes, including multilingualism in AI, ethical and explainable AI, AI in emergency services, and human-centric dialogue systems. Guests included leading researchers and partners from the ELOQUENCE consortium, who provided firsthand perspectives on the project’s advancements and the broader implications of trustworthy conversational AI.

In total, the ELOQUENCE podcast is planned to include **two seasons, each comprising six episodes**. By combining Webinars and Podcasts, ELOQUENCE aims to disseminate its innovative solutions, engage diverse stakeholders, and contribute to advancing conversational AI technology for a more efficient and impactful future.

4.4.2 Educational Engagements - Webinars & EU-wide training & capacity building workshops for business, industry and society

After M18, ELOQUENCE will place a strong emphasis on educational engagement, particularly through Webinars and EU-wide Training Sessions (KPIs 25 and 28), with a dedicated focus on connecting with stakeholders in the conversational AI community. These sessions are designed to provide valuable insights and practical knowledge to developers, researchers, and AI enthusiasts. By covering key areas such as conversational AI development, responsible implementation, and ethical AI practices, these activities will contribute to building a more informed and sustainable AI ecosystem.

Each webinar will be hosted via the **Zoom platform**, will last approximately **40 minutes** (including a Q&A session), and will target a broad audience of researchers, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and AI practitioners.

Speakers will include representatives from ELOQUENCE partner institutions, sister projects, and relevant European networks and platforms. INOSENS will coordinate the organization, technical setup, and moderation for each session.

The first ELOQUENCE webinar was successfully held in June 2025, led by our partner FBK in collaboration with Almawave company – available at ELOQUENCE YouTube channel. The session set the tone for upcoming webinars by addressing the core challenges and opportunities in the field of trustworthy AI and explainability. It also provided a platform for expert exchange and stakeholder interaction, reinforcing the project’s educational and outreach objectives.

ELOQUENCE will organize 9 more webinars bimonthly, serving as a forum for in-depth discussions led by project experts and key stakeholders. These webinars offer a unique opportunity to explore the project’s objectives, methodologies, and outcomes in detail. Through these sessions, ELOQUENCE seeks to promote best practices, encourage knowledge transfer, and strengthen ties with the broader research and industry community.

In the table below, we have listed the agreed partners who will be included as speakers in the upcoming webinars. Topics will be redefined based on their specific expertise and role within the project, ensuring relevance and value to the intended audience.

Table 5 Timeline for the ELOQUENCE webinars

Month	Title	Speaker (Partner)
June 2025	<i>Building Multilingual AI for Europe</i>	FBK
July 2025	<i>Bias Detection and Fairness in Language Technologies</i>	BUL
September 2025	<i>Trustworthy AI in High-Stakes Applications</i>	IDIAP
November 2025	<i>Ethical AI and Human Rights: Challenges for Policymakers</i>	Ethics Advisory Board + EUI
January 2026	<i>Knowledge Infusion and Reducing Hallucinations in LLMs</i>	BUT
March 2026	<i>Piloting AI: From Smart Homes to Call Centers</i>	CNR + UNS
May 2026	<i>Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning</i>	Telefónica + External Speaker (EDIC ALT connection)

July 2026	<i>Building Responsible AI Ecosystems: Networks and Standards</i>	PRIVANOVA + External (e.g., ADRA-e representative)
September 2026	<i>Human-in-the-Loop AI Systems for Critical Decision Making</i>	IDIAP + UNS
November 2026	<i>Exploitation and Innovation: Scaling ELOQUENCE Results</i>	Telefónica + INOSENS

4.4.3 Industry Engagements - Roadshow Events series & Live Virtual Demo Days and Q&A with Pilots

In line with the ELOQUENCE Dissemination and Communication Plan, **roadshows** were conceived as an opportunity for project partners to present ELOQUENCE developments, engage with relevant stakeholders, and foster connections within local, national, and international ecosystems. Over the course of the first 18 months of the project, consortium partners **actively participated in 31 events** (main are listed in the table below), including workshops, conferences, and community gatherings where they presented the goals, pilots, and scientific contributions of ELOQUENCE. These engagements served not only to raise awareness of the project but also to facilitate collaborations and encourage dialogue with representatives from academia, industry, and public institutions.

Table 6 ELOQUENCE Roadshow events

Event Name	Aim
Open Day at FTS UNS	Boosting the capacity of our academic institution to participate in European projects such as ELOQUENCE.
Info Day at FTS UNS	Foster collaborations
Brunel University of London - EEE presentation to the Industrial Advisory panel	Increase knowledge
Interspeech 2024	Dissemination of research
ACL 2024	Build upon and refine existing knowledge and related techniques
Conference on minority languages organized by a local Cultural institute for a local Germanic language in Trentino	Inform local authorities
Keynote Speech at 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	Increase knowledge
Building Bridges with Industry @ CLARIN2024	Foster more effective knowledge, data and technology transfer in order to accelerate technological advancements and create broader societal benefits

40th International Conference of the Spanish Society for Natural Language Processing

Dissemination of research

Infocom 2024	The event brought together various projects working on around Data
Jelinek Summer Workshop on Speech and Language Technology	Fostering collaboration on the aspects of dialog modelling for highly risky scenarios
26th International Conference on Speech and Computer	Increase awareness about the project
32nd Telecommunications Forum	Increase awareness about the project
AISV 2025	Increase knowledge, improve language technologies
ICLR 2025	Advance State of the art on Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)
21st International Conference on Natural Language Processing	The conference provided an invaluable platform to raise awareness of the ELOQUENCE project within the global community
The Fifth Workshop on SOcial and Cultural IntegrAtion with PersonalIZED Interfaces (SOCIALIZE'25)	Foster collaborations with scientific network
ICASSP 2025	Awareness of project results related to the use of audio, speech and language models for Automatic speech recognition
Interspeech 2025	Dissemination of research
European Research and Innovation Days 2025	Inform decision makers and foster collaboration

Each partner leveraged their networks to highlight specific aspects of ELOQUENCE, from multilingual AI and speech technologies to standardization and ethical AI implementation, ensuring broad and consistent visibility throughout the wider research and innovation landscape. These participatory activities collectively reflect the project's commitment to embedding itself in the wider European AI ecosystem and in engaging with domain-relevant communities across Europe and beyond. Partners will announce their participation in the following events:

- IEEE International Conference on Metrology for eXtended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXRAINE 2025);
- 16th Biannual Conference of the Italian SIGCHI Chapter on “Technologies and Methodologies of Human-Computer Interaction in the Third Millennium”;
- Challenge and Workshop on Multilingual Conversational Speech Language Model (MLC-SLM);

- Jelinek Summer Workshop on Speech and Language Technology - JSALT 2025;
- AI, Data and Robotics Forum (ADRF25).

In addition to roadshows, ELOQUENCE organized and recorded **four Virtual Demo Days**, each dedicated to one of the project's pilot applications. These recordings were captured during the **second day of the Plenary Meeting held in November 2024 in Novi Sad**, hosted by the UNS. The second day of the meeting was open to the public and served as a valuable opportunity to promote the project to the local scientific and technology community, including researchers, students, and innovation stakeholders. Each pilot presentation showcased the technological progress made within ELOQUENCE and allowed project members to receive early feedback and questions from attendees.

All four Virtual Demo Day presentations have been published on the **ELOQUENCE [YouTube channel](#)**, where they are publicly accessible and serve as educational and promotional content for wider dissemination.

4.5 Publications & Academic Liaisons

4.5.1 Academic Contributions: Peer-Reviewed Papers & Conferences

ELOQUENCE is committed to the principles of Open Science, ensuring that all research outputs are **accessible, transparent, and reusable in line with European Union standards**. Upholding the values of scientific integrity and collaborative knowledge sharing, ELOQUENCE has chosen to disseminate its findings through established peer-reviewed journals relevant to the fields of AI, natural language processing, and multilingual technologies.

Rather than utilizing the Open Research Europe platform, the consortium has strategically selected high-impact scientific publications to maximize visibility and engagement within targeted research communities. A full list of the published articles is available on the [ELOQUENCE Publications Page](#), where visitors can explore the scientific contributions made by the project to date.

All publications produced within the project are deposited in Zenodo, an open-access platform developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. This guarantees secure archiving and broad dissemination of ELOQUENCE's scientific contributions.

Zenodo offers a range of benefits that support ELOQUENCE's communication and dissemination strategy:

- *Open Access*: All publications are freely available to the global research community, supporting transparency and knowledge exchange.
- *Persistent Identifiers*: Each deposited work is assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), ensuring reliable citation, traceability, and academic visibility.
- *Data Sharing*: In addition to publications, related datasets and supplementary materials can be uploaded, enhancing reproducibility and research integrity.
- *EU Compliance*: Zenodo supports compliance with Horizon Europe's open-access requirements, helping ensure the project fulfills its obligations.
- *Multidisciplinary Visibility*: As a broad-reaching repository, Zenodo enables ELOQUENCE results to reach diverse audiences across multiple scientific and technical domains.

This approach ensures that ELOQUENCE's output remains accessible, discoverable, and reusable long after the project's completion.

ELOQUENCE partners are dedicated to disseminating project results through high-impact, peer-reviewed journals and magazines that align with the project's objectives and open science practices. An indicative list of future publication outlets includes journals and prestigious conferences: *Scientific Data*, *Interspeech*, *ACL Anthology*, *AISV*, *NAACL - Demo Track*, *International Conference of Learning Representations (ICLR)*, *ICASSP*, *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing Workshops (ICASSPW)*.

4.5.2 Industry Publications: Outlets with a focus on technology and AI

ELOQUENCE is committed to positioning itself at the forefront of AI language technologies in the EU, with targeted outreach efforts planned to scale significantly from Month 19 onward. As part of this strategy, the project aims to secure at least 85 editorial backlinks in top-tier online business and technology outlets such as *Tech.eu*, *TechCrunch*

Europe, Sifted, ComputerWeekly, DigiTimes Europe, and EURACTIV Digital. These backlinks will serve to enhance project visibility, support SEO objectives, and engage a wider industry and policy audience.

To date, we have already recorded **13 editorial backlinks**, as highlighted in the chapter on *Media Appearances and Press Releases*. These initial entries lay the groundwork for our intensified engagement with key media and industry channels during the upcoming project period.

All consortium partners acknowledge the importance of industry visibility and are actively exploring opportunities to showcase ELOQUENCE's innovations. Starting from M19, this objective will be further supported through proactive outreach and dedicated content placement. To ensure accountability and alignment, partners are required to track their contributions through the Comms & Dissemination Reporting Template (Annex A), enabling regular performance assessment and strategic adjustment.

4.6 EU-Level Liaison & Policy Influence

4.6.1 Industry Collaborations

Starting from M19, ELOQUENCE will intensify its focus on industry collaboration as a central component of its exploitation strategy. In this new phase, INOSENS, in cooperation with project partner Tree Logic (TL), will initiate the development of a dedicated Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) template to support engagement with relevant industrial stakeholders. These MoUs will serve as a foundation for future partnerships aimed at translating ELOQUENCE's research outputs into practical, market-oriented solutions.

INOSENS and TL will coordinate efforts to identify and reach out to key actors across the AI language technologies sector, ensuring a holistic and well-targeted approach. The exploitation of project results through industry cooperation is a priority, and a Key Performance Indicator has been set to secure **at least 10 MoUs or Letters of Intent (LoIs) with Industry Associations and Groups**. This collaborative industry engagement will lay the groundwork for scaling up project innovations in the later stages of ELOQUENCE.

4.6.2 Alliances & Partnerships

Establishing strategic alliances and partnerships is essential for embedding ELOQUENCE within the broader European AI ecosystem and maximizing the impact of its outcomes. During the first 18 months of the project, we successfully initiated collaborations with two Horizon Europe sister projects—[TrustLLM](#) and [MEETWEEN](#)—focusing on mutual learning, shared resources, and coordinated dissemination efforts. In parallel, synergies were also formed with four complementary initiatives and startups: [BIAS](#), [FindHR](#), [AI4REALNET](#), and [Enidia AI](#), expanding our collaboration into domains such as algorithmic fairness, ethical hiring, trustworthy AI for energy systems, and private-sector applications of multilingual LLMs.

ELOQUENCE has also joined forces with [AI-on-Demand Platform](#) to share research outputs and contribute to the platform's knowledge base, and has become excellent collaboration with [ADRA-A](#), the European Partnership on Artificial Intelligence, Data and Robotics, positioning the project within influential EU-level networks. These connections support the project's goals of visibility, scalability, and knowledge transfer.

Our wider collaboration strategy incorporates EU-wide training and capacity-building workshops targeted at industry, academia, and civil society, the development of practice abstracts, interactive virtual demo days with pilots, live Q&A sessions, and curated meetups. We also plan annual roundtable discussions with our Lighthouse Committee to explore project alignment with market and policy needs.

To support the policy dialogue and regulatory foresight, ELOQUENCE will conduct online policy workshops and standardization-focused roundtables that bring together diverse stakeholders to reflect on results and propose actionable insights for future AI governance. All consortium members are actively contributing to identifying and cultivating these partnerships, leveraging their networks to ensure broad participation and engagement.

In the coming period, ELOQUENCE aims to expand and to strengthen connections with strategic European alliances, such as the *Alliance for Language Technologies (ALT-EDIC)*, *Language Technology Solutions*, *Language Data Space*, *European AI Alliance*, *EurAI (European Association for Artificial Intelligence)*, *AIOTI (Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation)*, *AI Watch*, and *the network of European Digital Innovation Hubs*. These relationships will reinforce our ambition to be at the forefront of responsible, multilingual AI development in Europe.

4.6.3 Investment Relations

INOSSENS has prepared a dedicated Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) template to support collaboration with potential industrial partners and investors, along with a draft NDA to facilitate secure discussions. While foundational engagement has started, the bulk of activities targeting the investment and industry community is planned for Period 3 (starting from M19) of the project (inputs for D7.3), aligning with the readiness of ELOQUENCE pilots and demonstrators. This timing will allow for a more compelling presentation of project outputs and their application potential.

All consortium partners will contribute to this effort by identifying relevant contacts across industry associations, accelerators, and innovation networks. These partnerships are expected to bring not only financial support but also strategic insight, domain knowledge, and market access, critical for the scale-up of ELOQUENCE technologies, including the Interactive Playground and multilingual AI models.

The project has set measurable goals in this area: **securing at least 10 MoUs or Letters of Intent (LoIs) with industry associations and groups, and at least 3 NDAs with investors or industrial stakeholders.** These KPIs reflect our long-term commitment to transforming research results into sustainable, scalable innovations within the AI and language technology ecosystems.

5 Comms & Dissemination Timeline

The indicative timeline for communication and dissemination activities in ELOQUENCE in D7.1 outlines a structured and strategic approach to stakeholder engagement and public outreach throughout the project’s three-year duration. This roadmap ensures a steady distribution of content, maintaining momentum and relevance while building relationships with key audiences across sectors.

It is important to note that the timeline reflects only the major planned activities. In parallel, ELOQUENCE maintains an active and consistent digital presence through multiple communication layers. Social media posts are published three times per week to ensure ongoing engagement, while bi-weekly blog posts offer in-depth coverage of project milestones, partner contributions, and thematic developments.

In addition to these regular outputs, ELOQUENCE leverages media outreach, search engine optimization (SEO), and link-building strategies to enhance discoverability and reach. Strategic engagement with EU-level stakeholders and institutions supports the project’s policy impact and aligns communication with broader European priorities.

Furthermore, capacity-building activities, synergy collaborations, and roadshow events are designed to run horizontally across the timeline, strengthening the project’s presence at both grassroots and institutional levels. These dynamic and interlinked efforts reflect ELOQUENCE’s comprehensive approach to communication, ensuring that all activities reinforce one another to maximize visibility, uptake, and long-term impact.

Dissemination activities in ELOQUENCE are designed based on the displayed phases, increasing in intensity as the project progresses.

Table 7 Communication phases

Phase	Dissemination Activity
<p>Phase I</p>	<p>Promoting Project Pilots and Disseminating Knowledge</p> <p>During Phase I of the ELOQUENCE project, our focus is on approach-oriented content. We actively promote project pilots and share existing knowledge related to our innovative solutions. This phase aims to provide valuable insights from validated learning and create awareness about the potential of ELOQUENCE.</p>
<p>Phase II</p>	<p>Sharing Intermediate and Final Results</p> <p>In Phase II, we shift our focus to result-oriented content. We will disseminate the intermediate results achieved throughout the project, showcasing the achievements of our pilots. This phase aims to highlight the tangible outcomes and advancements made by ELOQUENCE, generating interest and engagement from our target audience.</p>
<p>Phase III</p>	<p>Dissemination of Project Final Results and Analysis</p> <p>In Phase III, we will focus on sharing the project's results and achievements. This includes conducting various analyses and assessments of the project outcomes.</p> <p>To ensure wide visibility and reach, we will publish our research findings in reputable peer reviewed. Additionally, we will actively participate in conferences related to hydrology, water resources, and environmental sciences.</p>

6 Reporting, Monitoring, Evaluation

6.1 KPI's and Targets Overview

To maintain transparency and ensure continued alignment with our communication and dissemination objectives, the **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** and their respective targets, initially defined in Deliverable D7.1, have been further reviewed and updated in this document. These KPIs continue to serve as a strategic roadmap, guiding the consortium through each phase of the project. As the implementation of activities advances, particularly with the launch of pilots and increasing stakeholder engagement, these indicators allow us to track progress, evaluate impact, and make data-informed adjustments where necessary.

Table 8 ELOQUENCE – Dissemination and Communication KPIs

ID	KPI Title	KPI Target	Achieved
1	Brand Book and Guidelines	1	1
2	Digital-first dissemination materials: Brochures	4	1
3	Digital-first dissemination materials: factsheets	6	0
4	Miscellaneous materials (notebook, folder, roll-ups, banners, stickers, bags, caps)	1	1
5	Website Creation	1	1
6	Website views	75,000	12,434
7	Content Downloads	5,500	60
8	Blog posts	130	60
9	Press releases	7	1
10	Explainer videos	15	2
11	Social Media Accounts	6	7
12	Social Media Followers	3,500	1427
13	Newsletter Subscribers	1,200	314
14	Editorial Backlinks	85	13
15	Click-to-open rate	20-30%	28,57%
16	Participation in media	20	1
17	Web cafes	20	3
18	Podcast Seasons	2	1

19	Roadshow event	35	31
20	Virtual Demo Days	5	4
21	Industry-driven events and conferences	25+	31
22	Live Virtual Demo Days and Q&A with Pilots	4	0
23	Webinars	10	1
24	Meetups	5	0
25	Lighthouse Committee Roundtable	3	0
26	Innovation Challenges/ Hackathons	3	0
27	ELOQUENCE Pathways Collaboratory Showcase Final Event	1	0
28	Joint press releases	6	0
29	R&I Networks/ Platforms	30	8
30	Open access publications	30	16
31	Presentations (oral/poster)	25	4

32	Practice Abstracts	6	0
33	EU-wide training & capacity building	3	0
34	Online policy workshops	3	0
35	White paper	1	0
36	Standardization-focused roundtable	1	0
37	Liaison with Industry Associations & Groups	10	0
38	NDA's signed with investors and industrial partners to drive further fine-tuning, demonstration, and scaling of the Interactive Playground (IP) and models	3	0

This table provides a clear and structured overview of the project's **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)**, offering measurable targets that guide our efforts and help assess progress. It functions as an ongoing point of reference, ensuring that all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities remain aligned with the project's strategic objectives.

Importantly, the KPIs are dynamic and distributed across three reporting phases: **M1–M3, M3–M18, and M18–M36**. These intervals represent more than just timeframes; they reflect key stages in the project's development and implementation. Monthly interval reporting enables us to monitor performance consistently, adapt strategies, and maintain momentum.

The current reporting period, **M3–M18**, has focused on the execution and early results of activities established during the foundational phase (**M1–M3**). During this phase, we expanded stakeholder engagement, launched new digital initiatives including podcasts and webinars, amplified our social media presence, and refined internal communication protocols. Significant effort has also been invested in setting up mechanisms for synergy building and preparing for wider media engagement. As we transition to the **M18–M36** period, the emphasis will increasingly shift toward showcasing results from pilot activities, scaling dissemination, and fostering long-term impact through policy, standardization, and exploitation efforts.

6.2 Consortium Partners' Roles and Responsibilities in Dissemination and Communication

The implementation of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan remains a shared responsibility among all consortium partners, reinforcing the collaborative nature of ELOQUENCE. INOSENS, as the dissemination and communication manager, continues to coordinate efforts, monitor progress, and ensure alignment with the overall objectives of the DEC Plan. The active involvement of all partners has proven essential, as many tasks rely on their direct contributions to stakeholder engagement, content generation, and knowledge exchange.

Since the beginning of the project, partners have taken on responsibilities in both offline and online dissemination. Offline efforts include organizing events, participating in conferences, and contributing to the visibility of the project at external engagements. In parallel, partners have supported online activities by sharing updates, submitting content for news posts, videos, and social media, and promoting the project's platforms through their institutional channels. These joint efforts are key to sustaining an inclusive and impactful dissemination strategy that will continue to evolve throughout the remainder of the project lifecycle.

For successful dissemination and communication, partners should continue:

- Engage with and share **ELOQUENCE's social media content** and actively participate in discussions.
- When requested or through opportunities like **interviews, podcasts, newsletter and webinars**, contribute to our website.
- Suggest **relevant events and projects for liaisons**.
- Partners should actively present the project's concepts, ideas, and findings at every suitable opportunity.
- Work should be published in **conference proceedings, scientific journals**, and other relevant outlets.
- Engage in targeted discussions, presenting project developments in related **technical or standardization groups, forums, and platforms**.
- Organize national and local events to engage authorities, stakeholders, and end-users.
- Issue **press releases**, liaise with media contacts, and conduct mass media activities.

All partners, through their participation in external events, conferences, and contributions to online and offline publications, should aim to maximize the project's exposure and dissemination.

TID	IDIAP	CNR	BSC	FBK	BUL	UESSEX	UNS
5	2	4	2	4	4	3	6
EUI	BUT	PN	INO	TL	GX	OM	SYN
2	2	10	45	20	12	3	6

Figure 15 Partner Involvements and Inputs

6.3 Reporting on Dissemination and Communication Activities

It is a compulsory requirement for all project partners to report on their dissemination and communication activities on a monthly basis. This enables INOSENS, as the dissemination and communication manager, to monitor progress toward Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and provide timely and accurate updates to the European Commission.

The Annex A ELOQUENCE – Dissemination and Communication Logbook functions as the central tracking tool for systematically recording all communication and dissemination efforts carried out during the project. It is essential that partners regularly update the logbook as they engage in relevant activities, ensuring that no effort goes

undocumented. This proactive reporting enables INOSENS to identify trends, address communication gaps early, and maintain consistent messaging throughout the consortium.

At the end of each month, partners are kindly asked to complete the logbook, summarizing the dissemination actions they undertook during that period and announcing upcoming events, publications, etc. The logbook is available at the following link: <https://forms.gle/Ni73WjsASkrmtVdF7>.

To facilitate flexibility and ensure inclusivity, INOSENS also accepts updates via email or through social media engagement. Partners are encouraged to tag the official ELOQUENCE accounts when sharing related content on platforms such as X, LinkedIn, Instagram, or Bluesky. This additional method supports real-time documentation and enhances the project's visibility.

Furthermore, we urge all partners to proactively inform INOSENS about any upcoming events in which they plan to participate, providing relevant details such as the event title, location, date, and format. This coordination ensures alignment with ELOQUENCE's broader communication objectives.

Should any challenges or risks arise in the execution of dissemination and communication activities, partners are strongly encouraged to contact INOSENS without delay so that any issues can be promptly resolved in a collaborative and efficient manner.

7 Exploitation Pathway

7.1 IPR

At the current stage of the ELOQUENCE project, no updates regarding Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) have been formally reported by the consortium members. The management of IPR remains alignment with the principles and mechanisms outlined in the Grant Agreement and the initial Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan submitted in Deliverable D7.1.

The consortium acknowledges the importance of IPR in ensuring that project results can be appropriately protected, shared, and exploited. Each partner retains the ownership of the results it generates, as agreed in the Consortium Agreement. Where results are generated jointly, partners are encouraged to enter into joint ownership agreements, as per the provisions of the Grant Agreement.

We kindly invite all partners to continue monitoring the development of exploitable results and to report any relevant IPR activities—including patents, licenses, trademarks, or design rights—through the periodic reporting tools. Any updates to the IPR status will be included in subsequent deliverables (notably D7.3) and may be reflected in a revised Exploitation Plan, should the need arise.

Until then, the project continues to operate within the established legal framework and encourages partners to engage in discussions related to IPR management as results mature and new opportunities for protection and exploitation emerge.

7.2 ELOQUENCE Exploitation Plan

7.2.1 Review and Enhancement of Exploitation Plan

The exploitation plan provided provides updates on previously proposed plan. Plan outlines three main pillars guiding the Eloquence project's exploitation activities, focusing on market analysis, responsiveness to market needs, and preparation for commercialization. While the plan demonstrates a structured approach to exploitation, incorporating startup market discovery approaches can enhance its effectiveness in identifying market opportunities and achieving product-market fit. The complete process started a little later than foreseen in the original exploitation plan to give developing teams time to focus on pilot delivery. A broader workshop was conducted at a plenary meeting to synchronise the understanding of our task and the activities that will take place, and it provided an intro into pilot dedicated workshops. Here's a proposed improvement incorporating lean principles into product design:

7.2.2 Objectives of Exploitation Strategy

Our primary objective is to leverage European principles in language learning to develop an innovative virtual assistant that caters to the diverse linguistic and cultural landscape of Europe. Furthermore, we aim to employ startup principles, particularly inspired by Lean Startup methodology and Geoffrey Moore's "Crossing the Chasm," to identify correct customers and capitalize on market opportunities, ensuring a smooth transition from research to market adoption.

1. Integration of Customer-Centric Approach: In addition to understanding end-user needs, it's imperative to educate the research teams on the significance of constant feedback from the market. This involves highlighting that ongoing interaction with potential customers helps in validating assumptions, refining product features, and ensuring alignment with evolving market demands. TL will provide training for all 4 pilot research teams to view customer feedback as essential input for guiding product development decisions throughout the project lifecycle.

TL has conducted an introductory workshop for the whole consortia at a plenary meeting in the month of February.

We are starting to implement this in a 6 module 2 h per module Data Driven approach theoretical workshops for all the prototype teams individually. Data driven decision making modules will serve as guiding principles for the work done in the next step.

The modules' topics will be:

1. **Intro** - Introduction to data driven philosophy, business modelling framework and lean processes. Teams form an understanding of product market fit and what it means for a startup.
2. **Market** - Market introduction and market segmentation. Teams will learn about targeting their market, predicting the size of the market, market timing, segmenting markets and choosing the appropriate segment to target.
3. **User** - The aim is to teach teams to look at the world from their customers' point of view so they can truly understand their customers. They will learn how to conduct experiments to prove their segment, find their ideal customer and understand their problems to be able to build their customer experience journey and decompose the problem they are solving on partial problems and learn to understand their value.
4. **Value Proposition** - Based on user understanding we will learn how to prepare value propositions for given users and build value proposition canvases.
5. **Strategy** - We will cover going to market strategy, based on problem map – market map, market/segment entry barriers and problem size. We will also determine how to set globalization and technology components of going to market strategy.
6. **MVP and lean analytics** - Based on their Value Proposition canvas and going to market strategy the teams decide on MVP and their minimal feature list. Teams will learn about feature driven design, fast prototyping and lean analytics.

2. Agile Development and Iterative Prototyping: Research teams will be educated on the importance of incorporating constant feedback from the market into the agile development process. They will learn that rapid prototyping and iterative cycles are not only about internal adjustments but also about responding to external market signals. By understanding this, teams can effectively adapt the product to meet evolving customers' needs and preferences in real time.

Figure 16 ELOQUENCE Exploitation Strategy

This step will be taken by Transformation Lighthouse team with the help of each research group's point of contact (1 from each pilot team). We will conduct primary customer research by talking directly to potential consumers. We will implement all the points from previous theoretical parts, especially point 2. market segmentation and point 3. Hypothesis testing. Through this continues process of hypothesis assessment and interviews with potential

customers we will get out our market segment, the barrier to enter for different segments and our main value proposition.

We cannot stress the importance of this process. If this process is done correctly, we will get a whole market segmentation through customers' eyes, our direct path of further development of LLM-based agents technology and already direct contact with the potential customers.

3. Validation through Customer Discovery: The emphasis on customer discovery will include educating research teams on the critical role of continuous feedback in validating assumptions and ensuring product-market fit. They will learn that customer interviews, surveys, and usability tests serve not only to gather data but also to iteratively refine the product based on real-world insights. This understanding will be very important after the prototype stage when research teams are asked to prioritize customer feedback as a fundamental aspect of the validation process.

4. Building an external partnership, opening up the innovation:

Throughout the process of customer discovery the project has great opportunities to build relationships/connections to the market, making the project feel more open and collaborative. We will exploit these connections and after defining the segment and search for possible partners that would be willing to market certain solutions as a result of the Eloquence project.

7.2.3 Phases of Exploitation Strategy

Market Insights and Customer Discovery (M1-M10): In addition to gaining insights into market trends, research teams will be trained to actively engage with potential customers to understand their perspectives, pain points, and evolving needs. This early education will emphasize the importance of incorporating market feedback into the project's direction from the outset. This is especially important because the landscape of virtual agents and assistants is moving at such rapid speed, and it is hard to foresee where outside more general technology will go.

2. Prototype Development and MVP Iteration (M10-M20): Once we reach the prototype stage research teams will be guided to continuously iterate on prototypes based on feedback gathered from potential customers. They will learn to view MVP iterations not only as technical adjustments but also as opportunities to refine the product based on market insights, ensuring that subsequent iterations better address customer needs. MVP is the first tool for gathering insight from the market.

3. Business Model Validation (M12-M24): During the validation phase, research teams will be educated on the role of customer feedback in assessing the viability of different business models. They will understand that experiments conducted to test pricing strategies, revenue streams, and distribution channels should be informed by ongoing interactions with potential customers to ensure alignment with market realities.

4. Go-to-Market Strategy and Scaling (M25-M36): As the project progresses, research teams will be encouraged to continuously gather feedback from the market to define different development channels for different applications. They will learn to adapt marketing channels, partnerships, and sales tactics based on evolving customer preferences, thereby ensuring that the product launch and scaling efforts are guided by real-world insights. The main goal is to:

- **Launch Full-Scale Product:** Based on insights gathered from pilot tests and iterative development, launch the full-scale version of the virtual assistant in the European market, ensuring compliance with quality standards and regulatory requirements.
- **Sales and Distribution Expansion:** Establishing partnerships with resellers, distributors, and online marketplaces to increase accessibility.
- **Customer Support and Engagement:** Prioritize customer support and engagement initiatives to foster long-term relationships with users, providing timely assistance and continuously improving the product based on user feedback.
- **Monitor Performance and Adapt:** Continuously monitor the performance of virtual assistants and LLM-based agents in the market, tracking key metrics such as sales, user engagement, and customer satisfaction, and adapt the strategy as needed to capitalize on emerging opportunities

7.2.4 Desired/possible outcomes

- Detailed market analysis of virtual assistant's viability and customer segments, Formal publications/articles/book on Customers/market understanding the relationship to LLMs.
- Defining an industry partner or technology partner (beyond consortium members) that is interested in implementing and selling virtual assistant or agent – use cases. Working together with research groups optimising the new system creating a collaborative effort.
- Creating an internal spinoff with research/development teams creating a new entity focused only on software LLM-based agent's other potentials.

7.2.5 Conclusion

By integrating education on the importance of constant feedback from the market into both the objectives and phases of the exploitation strategy, the ELOQUENCE project can empower research teams to effectively leverage customer insights throughout the project lifecycle. We are currently in the middle of this process starting with the pilot teams. We are at a point where we will start to talk and gather feedback from the potential clients recognized by the teams.

This proactive approach ensures that teams not only understand the significance of customer-centricity but also possess the necessary skills to continuously adapt the product to meet evolving market demands, ultimately increasing its competitiveness and market relevance.

In conclusion, our proposed exploitation strategy aims to harness the potential of European principles in language learning and startup methodologies to successfully commercialize and scale the virtual assistant in the European market. By following this strategic roadmap, we are confident in our ability to achieve sustainable market adoption and deliver significant value to our stakeholders.

Warning about these steps and the process will be subjected to change due to different factors:

- Different partnerships emerging
- Insights gather by doing primary research with potential clients
- Global LLM and agent technology changes (3 years ago world LLM and multi-agent hardly existed beyond research labs)
- Possible development challenges

8 Conclusion

Deliverable D7.2, (Mid-Term Update), builds on the foundation established in D7.1 by providing a detailed report on the progress made in communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities during the first 18 months of the ELOQUENCE project. This document outlines updates to the methodology, highlights achieved milestones and evaluates the effectiveness of the implemented strategies. It also identifies key strengths, addresses areas requiring improvement, and sets future directions for the next project phase.

The deliverable reflects the collective effort of all project partners in contributing to the successful execution of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, ensuring active engagement with stakeholders, increased visibility of project outcomes, and alignment with the project's overarching objectives. The planned future activities will focus on maintaining momentum in achieving the set KPIs, enhancing the dissemination of scientific and technological advancements, and fostering greater stakeholder involvement.

D7.2 serves as a roadmap for the continued implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts, ensuring the project remains on track to maximize its impact and effectively promote the use cases and other project outcomes in the coming phases.

Annex A Comms & Dissemination Activity Report

Impact and Outcome

Q7. What was the expected impact or outcome of this activity/output? (e.g., inform decision-making, foster collaborations, increase knowledge)

Your answer

Q8. Status of the Activity/Output:

Cancelled

Delivered

Ongoing

Postponed

Q9. Did this activity/output involve a formal publication or scientific presentation?

Choose

Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?

Choose

Article processing costs that will be charged to the project:

Your answer

Publication Details (Optional)

If this activity/output included a formal publication or presentation, please provide its reference details below

Type of PID (repository) for the Publication:

Choose

Publisher Version of Record PID:

Your answer

PID of Deposited Publication:

Your answer

Type of Publication:

Choose

Link to Publication (Data to be completed only if DOI not available):

Your answer

Title of the Scientific Publication (for book chapter, the title of chapter, not book):

Your answer

Authors (Data to be completed only if DOI not available):

Your answer

Title of the Journal or Equivalent:

Your answer

Number (if applicable):

Your answer

ISSN or eISSN:

Your answer

Publisher:

Your answer

Month of Publication:

Choose

Year of Publication:

Your answer

Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication?

Choose

Peer-Reviewed Status:

Choose

If a Book, PID of Book:

Your answer

ELOQUENCE - Dissemination and Communication Logbook

Welcome to the **ELOQUENCE Dissemination and Communication Logbook**. This form is designed to document the dissemination and communication activities of the ELOQUENCE project. We request that you submit your responses **once a month, at the beginning of each month**. Your contributions are vital for evaluating the impact of our activities and for meeting our reporting responsibilities to the EC. Please provide the most up-to-date information for each question. Be assured that all information will be treated with **confidentiality** and used exclusively for project reporting purposes.

mens.brđaric97@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

Not shared

Activity Information

Filled by *

Choose

Q1. Activity/Output Title:

Your answer

Q2. Brief Description (Please describe the main content or message of the activity/output) (200 characters max):

Your answer

Q3. Date(s) of Activity/Output:

Date

Reach and Purpose

Q4. Who was your primary audience for this activity/output? (Select all that apply)

- Industry/business partners
- Innovators
- EU institutions
- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities
- Civil society
- Citizens
- Research communities
- Specific and user communities
- International organisation (IM body, OECD, etc.)
- Other (Please Specify)
- Investors

Q5. What was the main purpose of this activity/output? (Select one that best applies)

- Sharing project findings or results
- Raising awareness about the project
- Engaging with stakeholders or the public
- Educating or training
- Other:

Format and Channels

Q6. Through what means did you conduct/share this activity/output? (Select all that apply)

- Event (Conference, Workshop, etc.)
- Exhibition
- Interview
- Media Article
- Newsletter
- Press Release
- Print Materials (Brochures, Leaflets, Posters, etc.)
- Social Media
- TV/Radio Campaign
- Video
- Website
- Clustering Activities
- Collaboration with EU-funded Projects
- Education and Training Events
- Meetings
- Other:

Further Comments and Feedback

Q11. Any other comments, feedback, or additional information you'd like to share about this activity/output?

Your answer

Q12. If you have any videos or images related to your dissemination and communication activities, please provide the links below.

Alternatively, you may upload them directly to the project's Nextcloud in the folder [0_Dissemination & Communication Logbook / Media](#).

Your answer

Annex B Press clipping / media monitoring

No.	Title	First seen on	Link	Language
1	New Projects in AI, Data and Robotics 2024 Edition	January 2024	https://adra-e.eu/sites/default/files/2024-03/CNECT_ERF2024_LR_002_6HTEUZvrKcJgbWlqwk9jbeTXHQ_103116.pdf	English
2	Multilingual and Cross-cultural interactions for context-aware, and bias-controlled dialogue systems for safety-critical applications	January 2024	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135916	English
3	ELOQUENCE - Multilingual and Cross-cultural interactions for context-aware, and bias-controlled dialogue systems for safety-critical applications	January 2024	https://www.icar.cnr.it/en/progetti/eloquence-multilingual-and-cross-cultural-interactions-for-context-aware-and-bias-controlled-dialogue-systems-for-safety-critical-applications/	English
4	A Dynamic and Self-Organized Artificial Swarm Intelligence Solution for Security and Privacy Threats in Healthcare ICT Infrastructures	March 2024	https://www.ahci.icar.cnr.it/eloquence/	English
5	ELOQUENCE - Multilingual and Cross-cultural interactions for context-aware, and bias-controlled dialogue systems for safety-critical applications	March 2024	https://inosens.rs/horizon-europe/eloquence-2/	English
6	Multilingual and Cross-cultural interactions for context-aware, and bias-controlled dialogue systems for safety-critical applications	March 2024	https://www.privanova.com/eu-projects/eloquence	English
7	ELOQUENCE AI4Europe	April 2024	https://www.ai4europe.eu/ai-community/projects/eloquence	English

8	ELOQUENCE Project Advances Multilingual Conversational AI for Safety-Critical Applications	July 2024	https://magazine.fbk.eu/en/news/eloquence-project-advances-multilingual-conversational-ai-for-safety-critical-applications/	English
9	ELOQUENCE webcafe with Saskia Lensink	December 2024	https://www.ai4europe.eu/news-and-events/events/web-cafe/eloquence-webcafe-saskia-lensink	English
10	ELOQUENCE webcafe Trustworthy AI: Why Explainability Matters?	May 2025	https://www.ai4europe.eu/news-and-events/events/web-cafe/eloquence-webcafe-trustworthy-ai-why-explainability-matters	English
11	Unveiling ELOQUENCE: Pioneering Conversational AI in Europe	May 2025	https://www.privanova.com/resources/unveiling-eloquence-pioneering-conversational-ai-in-europe	English
12	ELOQUENCE Project Advances Multilingual Conversational AI for Safety-Critical Applications	May 2025	https://inosens.rs/eloquence-project-advances-multilingual-conversational-ai-for-safety-critical-applications/	English
13	ELOQUENCE Project Mid-Term Update: Advancing Europe's Trustworthy Multilingual Conversational AI	June 2025	https://inosens.rs/eloquence-project-mid-term-update-advancing-europes-trustworthy-multilingual-conversational-ai/	English

